

Results and Discussion

In order to optimise reaction conditions the influence of tartaric acid, reagent concentration and time required for complete precipitation have been investigated.

Effect of Tartaric Acid and Reagent: Both tartaric acid and reagent concentration influence the rapid recovery of selenium (Table 2). Lower

TABLE-2 EFFECT OF TARTARIC ACID AND REAGENT CONCENTRATION ON SELENIUM DETERMINATION.

Se taken	Tartaric acid added.	Phenylhydrazine added	Digestion time	Se found	Recovery
mg	g	ml	hr	mg	%
49.50	2.0	0.15	3.0	49.30	99.6
49.50	2.0	0.50	3.0	49.40	99.8
24.75	2.0	1.00	3.0	24.75	99.8
24.75	2.0	2.00	3.0	24.68	99.8
9.90	2.0	5.00	3.0	9.89	99.9
49.50	5.00	0.15	3.00	49.40	99.8
99.00	10.00	0.15	3.00	98.90	99.9
24.75	20.00	0.15	3.00	24.70	99.9
24.75	30.00	0.15	3.00	24.70	99.9
49.50	5.00	0.15	0.5	35.05	70.8
24.75	10.00	0.30	0.5	22.10	89.3
24.75	20.00	0.50	0.5	24.70	99.9
9.90	30.00	0.50	0.5	9.86	99.6

acid concentrations prolonged the reaction time too long for practical purposes. Higher concentrations of tartaric acid were chosen in preference to lower acidities because the reduction of selenium occurred more readily at higher acidities and hydrolysable metals were easily kept in solution. The optimum conditions to achieve the rapid recoveries of the metal are 5 to 15% tartaric acid and 0.5 to 1 ml reagent in a final volume of 200 ml. To ensure rapid recoveries of the metal an excess of reagent (0.5-1 ml) is recommended. A large excess of the reagent upto 5 ml however has no adverse effect.

Time: The minimum digestion time required for the quantitative precipitation to be established by varying the amounts of tartaric acid and phenylhydrazine (Table 2). The selenium completely separated after a brief digestion period of 30 min with 10% tartaric acid and 5 ml reagent solution saving time with no sacrifice of accuracy (Table 1). At lower concentrations of both, the reaction needed 3 hr for completion and the precipitate must be allowed to stand preferably overnight.

Diverse Ions: The method permits the determination of selenium in the presence of appreciable amounts of iron, cobalt, cadmium, manganese, nickel, chloride, sulphate and nitrate. Copper, tellurium, chromium and thorium, however, seriously interfere.

Use of Hydrochloric Acid: The reduction to elemental selenium is also accomplished in hydrochloric acid media at boiling water bath temperature. The reaction is complete in 1.0-6.0 N hydrochloric acid, (approximately 10 to 60% by volume). 40 ml of the acid in the total volume of 200 ml was used. The effect of acidity and the time required for complete precipitation are shown in Table 1. The experiments were made by taking varying amounts of selenium as selenious acid adding from 20-60 ml of hydrochloric acid and 5 ml of the reagent. Selenium was determined by the same procedure. In every case the recovery of selenium was quantitative. The precipitation of selenium as its black variety is accomplished in about 30 min. Hydrochloric acid is thus a convenient alternative to tartaric acid.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to D. B. Asthana, Director of Geology & Mining, Raipur (M. P.) for his constant encouragement and provision of laboratory facilities.

References

- G. J. MISHRA and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 560.
- R. A. NADKARNI and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 813.
- S. S. R. MURTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 298.
- V. LENHER and C. H. KAO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 769.
- V. LENHER and C. H. KAO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 245.
- V. HOVORKA, Collection, *Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1932, 4, 300.
- S. OABA and S. UNEO, *Talanta*, 1975, 22, 51.
- R. DOLIQUE, J. GIROUX and S. ROEA, *Bull. Soc. Chem.*, 1943, 10, 49.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd Edition, Longmans Green, London, 1962, p. 508.

Kinetics of Oxidation of Oxalic Acid by Ceric Sulphate in Acidic Medium

B. D. KANSAL, NEPAL SINGH
Hindu College, Moradabad, U.P.

and

HAMBIR SINGH
D. S. College, Aligarh, U. P.

Manuscript received 21 June 1976, accepted 26 September 1977

CERIC sulphate is one of the strongest oxidising agents with an oxidation potential of 1.43 ± 0.05 Volts in 1-8N sulphuric acid¹. The common valencies of cerium in ceric salts are 3 and 4, in which the probable unhybridised electronic configuration² are $5s^2 5p^6 4d^{10} 4f^1$ and $5s^2 5p^6 4d^{10}$ respectively. The kinetic behaviour of the oxidation

of organic substrates by ceric ion present certain interested features. The reference may be given by the studies of α -hydroxy acids done by Dayal and Bakore³. The literature shows that only a preliminary work has been done on the oxidation of oxalic acid⁴⁻⁵ by Ce(IV). We have carried out a detailed kinetic study of oxidation of oxalic acid by ceric sulphate to obtain a deep insight into the reactive species of ceric sulphate.

Experimental

The chemicals used were either "AnalaR or E. Marck's" guaranteed reagent quality. Ce(IV) sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving ceric sulphate in sulphuric acid. The reactive substances were brought to the thermostat temperature maintained to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and then quickly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and the reaction was quenched by adding ice-cold distilled water and the unconsumed Ce(IV) was estimated with the standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin as an indicator. The observed pseudo first order rate constant k was calculated from the graph.

Effect of oxalic acid :

To study the effect of oxalic acid concentration, the reaction was carried out at five different initial concentration of oxalic acid and the same initial concentration of sulphuric acid and ceric sulphate. The kinetic data for these studies are summarised in Table-1.

TABLE-1

$10^3 \times [\text{Ce(IV)}] = 0.40 \text{ M}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.50 \text{ M}$;
Temp. = 25°

$10^3 \times [\text{Oxalic acid}] \text{ M}$	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50
$10^3 \times k(\text{min.}^{-1})$	6.48	8.18	10.18	11.64	14.50

The reaction is found to be pseudo first order w.r.t. oxalic acid which is confirmed by plotting $1/k$ Vs. $1/[\text{oxalic acid}]$. The plot is a straight line which cuts $1/k$ axis at a certain distance (Fig. 1).

Effect of Sulphuric Acid :

The effect of sulphuric acid concentration on the reaction has been studied at five different concentration of sulphuric acid as shown in Table-2.

TABLE-2

$10^3 \times [\text{Ce(IV)}] = 0.40 \text{ M}$; $10^3 \times [\text{Oxalic acid}] = 0.30 \text{ M}$;
Temp. = 25°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] \text{ M}$	1.50	2.00	2.50	3.00	4.50
$10^3 \times k(\text{min.}^{-1})$	13.56	11.39	10.18	9.41	8.18

The plot of k vs. $1/[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2$ is a straight line (Fig. 2) which indicates that the rate of reaction is inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of sulphuric acid.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Effect of Temperature :

The reaction has been studied at different temperatures varying from 288°A to 303°A. The Arrhenius parameters have been calculated and are recorded in Table-3.

The above stoichiometric equation is in conformity with the mole ratio 1 : 2 between oxalic

TABLE—3

Temp. in °A	$K \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	Energy of activation(E) in Kcals mole ⁻¹	Frequency factor (A) litre mole ⁻¹ $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{A} \times 10^{-4}$	Energy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) e.u.	Free energy (ΔG^\ddagger) Kcals mole ⁻¹
288	5.12	-	30.68	- 35.48	22.21
293	8.43	12.24	30.00	- 35.29	22.32
298	10.18	12.58	30.45	- 35.58	22.58
303	15.76	-	30.70	- 35.31	22.68
	Mean	12.58	30.65	- 35.41	22.44

Discussion

The plot of $1/k$ vs. $1/[\text{oxalic acid}]$ is a straight line which cuts $1/k$ axis at a certain distance. This suggests the formation of activated complex between Ce(IV) and oxalic acid. The activated complex decomposes into organic free radical and Ce(III) through chain mechanism as shown below :

The overall oxidation reaction may be written as :

acid and Ce(IV) as determined experimentally. The rate of consumption of Ce(IV) is given by reaction (i) as :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = K_1[\text{Ce(IV)}][\text{Oxalic acid}] \quad \dots(i)$$

According to Hardwick and Robertson⁶, the reactive specie ceric sulphate in presence of sulphuric acid gives the complexes as shown below :

Where K_2 and K_3 are the equilibrium quotients ;

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{HCe(SO}_4)_3^-]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-][\text{Ce(SO}_4)_2]} \quad \dots(ii)$$

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{Ce(SO}_4)_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HCe(SO}_4)_3^-][\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad \dots(iii)$$

from equation (ii) and (iii)

$$[\text{Ce(SO}_4)_2] = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{Ce(SO}_4)_4^{2-}]}{K_2 K_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2}$$

Substituting the value of $\text{Ce(SO}_4)_2$ in equation (i)

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1[\text{H}_2\text{Ce(SO}_4)_4^{2-}][\text{Oxalic acid}]}{K_2 K_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2} \quad \dots(iv)$$

As the equilibria of the reaction (7) and (8) are rapid, the $\text{H}_2\text{Ce(SO}_4)_4^{2-}$ will be proportional to Ce(IV) and on assuming the centpercent dissociation of sulphuric acid into H^+ and HSO_4^- ion, the equation (iv) is reduced to the form :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = \frac{K'[\text{Ce(IV)}][\text{Oxalic acid}]}{K_2 K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2} \quad \dots(v)$$

For a given kinetic run, the concentration of sulphuric and acid oxalic acid will be constant. The equation (v) may be written as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ce(IV)}] \quad \dots(\text{vi})$$

Which is experimental rate equation for disappearance of Ce(IV) ion.

References

1. N. S. SHERRILL., C. G. KING., R. C. SPOONER., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 170.
2. G. F. SMITH, 'Cerate Oxidimetry', G. FEDRICK SMITH, Chemical Co., Columbus, Ohio, 1942.
3. R. DAYAL, and G. V. BAKORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 657.
4. A. BENRATH., and K. RULAND, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 114, 167.
5. V. H. DODSON and A. H. BLACK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 3657.
6. T. J. HARDWICK. and E. ROBERTSON., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1951, 29, 828.

Solid State Studies on Polymerization and Depolymerization of 12-Heteropoly Molybdochromate (III)

H. C. MISHRA, SALIL KUMAR ROY and A. N. OJHA
University Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University,
Ranchi-834008

Manuscript received 25 August 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

THE present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of a new condensation inorganic polymer, $\text{K}_5[\text{CrMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 36\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The oxidation state of chromium has been established by E.S.R. method and the studies on thermal depolymerization of the compound has also been carried. Of condensation inorganic polymer¹, very few references on heteropoly molybdochromate² are found in the literature. The present note is an attempt towards that line.

To 80 ml. of M/15 potassium dichromate solution, 50 ml. of M/10 aqueous solution of molybdic acid and 10 ml. of '20 volume' hydrogen peroxide solution was gradually added with constant stirring at a controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. The stirring was continued for two hours and then the solution was left for three days in vacuum, when orange coloured needle shaped crystalline compound came out which was recrystallised thrice from hot water. The analysis of the compound was carried out by usual chemical and colorimetric methods. Estimation of potassium has also been corroborated by flame photometric method. (Found : K, 7.10 ; Mo, 42.65 ; Cr, 1.80 ; H, 2.50% Cald. for $\text{K}_5[\text{CrMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 36\text{H}_2\text{O}$: K, 7.25 ; Mo, 42.87 ; Cr, 1.93 ; H, 2.67%). Hydrogen has been estimated by element

estimation method and molybdenum has been determined by colorimetric method³. From the analytical data, the molecular formula of the compound, as per Keggin's view³, comes out to be $\text{K}_5[\text{CrMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 36\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which may be named as 12-heteropoly molybdochromate.

Molecular Weight Determinations : The molecular weight of the polymeric compound has been determined accurately by X-ray crystal diffraction technique⁴. A single crystal of the compound was mounted along its longer dimension : a axis. By taking rotation and Weissenberg X-ray diffraction photographs, the values of unit cell dimensions were found to be $a=11.62$, $b=26.12$, $c=8.62 \text{ \AA}$ & $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$, volume per unit cell 'V' was calculated to be 2616.294 \AA^3 . No. of molecules per unit cell 'Z'=2. Pycnometric measurement gives the observed density $\rho_{\text{obs}}=3.38 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation, $\rho_{\text{obs}}=1.66 \text{ M.Z/V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound comes to 2664 against the calculated value 2687.

Measurement of Oxidation State of the Heteroatom : The E.S.R. spectra of the compound were recorded on the powdered sample, using varian 4502-15 E.S.R. spectrometer system, operating at 100 Kcps field modulation. The X ray band spectrum shows only one line at 3500 gauss, $g_{\text{eff}}=1.9919$ (77°K). The diluted sample e.s.r. spectra has several shoulders which permit a reasonably accurate assessment of D value being 0.16 cm^{-1} and λ being 0.1211. There is strong distortion from O_h symmetry. Obviously from the comparative chart, g_{eff} value of the compound indicates chromium to be present in +3 oxidation state having d^3 configuration. The relative spin concentrations were determined by multiplying the peak-to-peak height of the derivative signal by the square of the maximum slope width and absolute concentration were estimated by comparison with standard sample⁵.

Thermal Depolymerisation : The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied in the light of the investigations made by West and Andrieth⁶ and by Babad-Zakhryapin⁷ on a few heteropolytungstic acids. The apparatus used for this purpose was that described by Ray and Sinha⁸ with continuous pumping the depolymerised product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimations at some stages. The dissociation⁴ of the compound was observed at 80° under reduced pressure when twelve molecules of water were lost. Of the rests, seven water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice till 290°, above which they were completely removed. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at 450°, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of molybdenum and chromium which have been confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of 12-heteropoly molybdochromate is $450^\circ \pm 5^\circ$.